

Synthesis of New Dithiocarbamates as Potential Anthelmintic Antimicrobial and Insecticidal Agents

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Fourteen new N-aryl/alkyl/morpholino/piperidino/pyrrolidino dithiocarbamates have been synthesized as potent anthelmintic and were screened for anthelmintic activity against *Hymenolepis nana* infection in mice and insecticidal activity against male and female cockroaches (*Periplaneta americana*) and two for antimicrobial activity. Few showed significant insecticidal activity.

THE growing incidence of helminthes infection in rural areas of various agriculture based countries has clearly demonstrated the urgent need of an ideal anthelmintic drug. Esters of dithiocarbamic acids have clearly been established as the leading anthelmintic^{1,2,3}, insecticidal and herbicidal⁴ agents, and thiadiazoles are well known to possess nematocidal⁵, insecticidal⁶ and herbicidal⁷ properties. Hence it was considered worthwhile to synthesize the title compounds anticipating that the resulting compounds may have considerable potency.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

Chloroacetyl-2-amino-5-methyl thiadiazole (I): These were prepared by the condensation of acetic acid with thiosemicarbazide according to known methods. Chloroacetylation in benzene yielded I^{8,9}.

Ammonium salts of dithiocarbamic acids (II): Aryl amines were treated with ammonia and carbon disulphide to yield II¹⁰.

S-(2-acetylamino-5-methyl 1,3,4-thiadiazolyl)-N-aryl/alkyl/morpholino/piperidino/pyrrolidino dithiocarbamates: Chloroacetyl-amino-5-methyl 1,3,4-thiadiazole (0.01 mole) was added with constant stirring to a solution of ammonium salt of N-aryl/alkyl/morpholino/piperidino pyrrolidino dithiocarbamic acids (0.01 mole) in 20 ml of aqueous acetone. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 hr and evaporated to dryness. The residue was recrystallized from methanol to give the title compounds. The melting points and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Comp. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula
1.	Phenyl amino	226	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS ₂
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl amino	238	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS ₂
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl amino	258	82	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS ₂
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl amino	270	83	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS ₂
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl amino	166	76	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
6.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl amino	160	80	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
7.	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl amino	209	81	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ OS ₂
8.	<i>m</i> -Chloro phenyl amino	205	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ OS ₂
9.	<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl amino	215	81	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ OS ₂
10.	Dimethyl amino	248	86	C ₈ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS ₂
11.	Diethyl amino	218	85	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS ₂
12.	Morpholino	242	80	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
13.	Piperidino	226	80	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS ₂
14.	Pyrrolidino	252	82	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS ₂

Satisfactory C, H and N analyses ($\pm 0.4\%$) were obtained for all the compounds.

Results and Discussion

Insecticidal activity: The insecticidal activity was evaluated against adult male and female cockroaches (*P. americana*). The compounds were dissolved in acetone and the acetone solution

applied at a dose of 0.02 ml of 0.5% and 0.1% solution per cockroach with 10 replications per compound. The chemicals were injected between 4th and 5th abdominal segment on the ventral side and the treated insects were kept under observation for 40 hr. The activity of the compounds were compared with well known insecticide ethyl parathion.

Out of the compounds tested, two compounds S-(2-acetylamino-5-methyl 1,3,4-thiadiazolyl)-N-pyrrolidino dithiocarbamate and S-(2-acetylamino-5-methyl 1,3,4-thiadiazolyl)-N-piperidino dithiocarbamate were found to be most active, with a mean

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K. D. time of 6 and 10 hr, respectively. However, substitution by morpholine group decreased the insecticidal activity. Responses in case of the other amines were not significant.

Antifungal and antibacterial activity : Two compounds (Nos. 2 and 4) were tested for their anti-fungal and antibacterial activity but the response in both the cases was not significant.

Anthelmintic activity : All the compounds were tested against *H. nana* infection in mice according to the method of Witlock. These compounds were administered orally at a dose of 25 mg/kg with 10 replications per compound. After fasting for 24 hr the animals were dissected to count the worm present in the intestine but none of the compounds showed any significant activity.

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